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The transcriptional landscape of basal-like subtype breast cancer in humans: CCT2.

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Breast cancer in humans is a solid tumor type with distinct subtypes historically defined by the PAM50 molecular subtype classification scheme (1-3). We utilize, in this study, whole transcriptome technologies to define the transcriptional landscape of basal-like subtype human breast cancer (4, 5). We describe here differential expression of CCT2 in the subtype of human breast cancer known as basal-like.

We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technology, using only primary tumor tissues from patients with breast cancer of defined molecular subtype (4, 5) to perform differential gene expression analyses, for characterization, in molecular detail, of the tumor transcriptome of basal-like subtype breast cancer.

Methods

We utilized microarray datasets GSE45827 (4) and GSE87049 (5) for this global differential gene expression analysis of basal-like subtype human breast cancer in conjunction with the R-based computational differential gene expression software GEO2R. GSE45827 was generated using [HG-U133_Plus_2] Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array technology with $n=11$ normal breast tissues (control) and $n=41$ basal-like subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using GPL570. GSE87049 was generated using Affymetrix Human Gene 1.0 ST Array [transcript (gene) version] technology with $n=35$ normal breast tissues (control) $n=14$ primary breast tumors of basal-like subtype from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform GPL6244. We used an R-based bioinformatic tool to perform whole transcriptome co-regulation studies across multiple tissues (SEEK [6]). We utilized a computational tool to measure the influence of tumor gene expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer, in $n=1879$ patients (total), in $n=431$ basal subtype patients, in $n=596$ luminal A subtype patients, in $n=439$ luminal B subtype patients, in $n=362$ HER2+ patients, and $n=51$ normal-like subtype patients (7).

Rationale

Breast cancer in humans is a complex molecular entity that remains to be completely defined.

Results

We performed whole transcriptome profiling - subtraction analysis, also known as differential gene expression profiling - to identify and describe at the systems level the complete set of genes whose expression was most specifically activated or repressed in humans with the basal-like subtype of human breast cancer.

1. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: basal-like subtype.

$n=11$ normal breast tissues (human)

$n=41$ primary tumors (breast; human; basal-like)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
201946_s_at	5.44E-18	-12.921497	30.648779	-4.5978626	CCT2	552/29873	98.2

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and basal-like breast tumors, we discovered differential expression of chaperonin containing TCP1 subunit 2, encoded by CCT2 (located at 12q15) in basal-like breast cancer in humans (Chart 1). The expression of CCT2 changed more than 98% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CCT2 messenger RNA in basal-like subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CCT2 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to basal-like breast cancer.

2. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: basal-like subtype

$n=35$ normal breast tissues (human)

$n=14$ primary tumors (breast; human; basal-like)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
7957052	3.14E-07	-5.8930209	6.31338	-0.87923667	CCT2	2519/33297	92.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and basal-like breast tumors in a second microarray dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of CCT2 in basal-like breast cancer in humans (Chart 2). The expression of CCT2 here changed more than 92% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CCT2 messenger RNA in basal-like subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CCT2 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to basal-like breast cancer.

Thus, CCT2 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the basal-like breast cancer subtype in humans.

In breast cancer as in any solid tumor, the function of the gene identified by whole transcriptome differential gene expression cannot be assumed to be the same as in non-transformed tissues. Thus, to identify gene products likely to interact with and/or be relevant to the differentially expressed genes function in the transformed tissue, we performed whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation studies using SEEK, an R-based computational tool that blindly and quantitatively identifies co-expression across the genome using a clustering method rather than integration-based differential gene expression methodology (6). This second whole transcriptome technology identified NUP107, PTGES3, CCT4, DHX9, HSPA8 as the five genes across the transcriptome most closely co-regulated with CCT2 in the transformed human breast (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed human breast: CCT2.

Finally, we measured the influence of CCT2 tumor gene expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer (**Figure 2**) (7).

Fig. 2: Relationship between CCT2 tumor expression and overall survival in humans with breast cancer.

Caption: Overall survival in all patients (above; left), in patients with basal subtype (above; center), in patients with luminal A subtype (above; right), in patients with luminal B subtype (below; left), in patients with HER2+ subtype (below; center), and patients with normal-like subtype breast cancer (below; right) is depicted in these Kaplan-Meier plots.

Discussion

We describe here CCT2 as a component gene product of the basal-like subtype in human breast cancer, suggesting its importance in the development or maintenance of the subtype, a product of tumor evolution in transformation of solid tissues in humans.

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